

DELAMINATION DETECTION IN LAMINATED GLASSY POLYMERS AND POLYMERIC COMPOSITES BY MEANS OF STRAIN SOLITONS

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ABSTRACT

The formation and evolution of strain solitary waves in waveguides made of glassy polymers (PMMA, polystyrene and polycarbonate) has been thoroughly investigated by us both experimentally and theoretically. The strain soliton behaviour in laminated bonded and delaminated waveguides made of these materials shows specific features depending upon various factors, including characteristics of an adhesive and even the number of layers in the laminated structure. The observed phenomena include formation of soliton trains in the delaminated area with the number of secondary solitons depending upon the number of layers; formation of radiating solitons in the case of rubber-like adhesives etc. More complicated wave patterns are generated if layers in a laminated waveguide are made of different materials. While a unified soliton propagates in a bonded area, in the delaminated area separate solitons propagate in layers, with different velocities that are characteristic for each material. This effect provides an immediate evidence of the delamination existence and its location. In the present paper we demonstrate soliton behaviour in various bonded and delaminated layered waveguides made of glassy polymers and composites and discuss their potentials for being used as a reliable tool for fast delamination detection in lengthy laminated structures. The application of solitons is attractive since it is the only bulk elastic wave which does not decay much even at long distances. The soliton recording was performed using the technique of holographic interferometry that allows one to obtain in a single shot a complete wave pattern in the waveguide within the area of several centimeters in diameter. The technique provides information on the soliton amplitude, shape, width and velocity.

1 INTRODUCTION

A considerable attention in fracture physics and technology of composite materials on the base of plastics is paid to delamination processes occurring in multi-layered adhesively bonded elements. In general mechanical characteristics of an adhesive may differ considerably from those of adherend material(s). That may result in an unexpected behaviour of the structure itself or in a degenerated adhesive strength. Disbonds or delamination areas may be caused by the presence of contaminants on an adherend surface, or can occur as a result of impacts, environmental degradation, ageing, or emerge in the course of usage of the bonded structure. The major problem in the behaviour of laminated structures consists in a possibility of a sudden and irreversible delamination under dynamic loading.

We consider a new technique that might be of use for nondestructive testing of adhesively bonded layered structures under their dynamic loading by bulk nonlinear strain solitary waves (strain solitons for brevity). Bulk strain soliton is a long non-linear localized traveling wave formed, under certain conditions, in a solid waveguide from an initial elastic impulse. A possibility to generate and register these bulk nonlinear strain waves in various materials was shown in our previous studies (see [1-9] and references therein), in particular, in polymeric layered structures with certain adhesive bondings [5,7]. Being formed, the soliton propagates along the homogeneous waveguide with almost no change of amplitude, shape and velocity [1]. In inhomogeneous waveguides the soliton parameters vary, depending upon parameters of inhomogeneities [2,4].

The basic principle of strain soliton formation in a solid wave guide can be briefly described as follows. The wave generation in a nonlinearly elastic waveguide can be initiated by a short and strong wave of deformation (a weak shock wave, for instance), propagating along it. However, the gradient of a wave front may quickly increase yielding irreversible deformations, provided the non-linear elasticity is not balanced with the wave dispersion in a solid waveguide (having small, but not infinitesimal cross section). Moreover, in absence of balance caused by various factors, e.g., by the nonlinearity of an opposite sign with respect to the strain sign in a propagating wave, the initial pulse decays very rapidly. The balance of an elastic nonlinearity of a waveguide material and a dispersion in a waveguide results in the bulk soliton generation, resistive to main mechanisms of elastic energy decay, quite stable and having permanent shape when moving along a considerable distance.

Previous theoretical and experimental research has been devoted to the generation and propagation of bulk strain solitary waves in various waveguides made of glassy polymers: polystyrene (PS), plexiglas (PMMA) and polycarbonate (PC). Strain solitons have been successfully generated in rods, bars and plates. The soliton focusing in a tapered rod has also been observed. The process of soliton dissipation has been studied in long thin bars (over half a meter long, one square cm in cross section). The experiments demonstrated that the wave is resistant to the usual causes of decay, is quite stable, has a permanent shape and can propagate for a considerable distance. Therefore, bulk solitary waves may transfer elastic energy for long distances with no significant losses.

2 EXPERIMENTAL APPROACH

2.1 Experimental setup

Experiments on generation and observation of bulk strain solitons in layered bars were performed using the experimental setup applied in our former research on nonlinear bulk elastic waves in various waveguides (see e.g. [1,2]). The experimental technique is based on laser generation and subsequent holographic recording of the waves under study. First the strain soliton is formed in the uniform PMMA rod from the initial shock wave generated in water nearby its input cross section via laser evaporation of the metallic foil (see Fig. 1). The rod (10 mm in diameter, 50 mm long) is bonded to the layered bar (10x10 mm cross section) with layers made of PMMA and/or PS. The two types of waveguides are used in experiments: one with layers completely bonded by the ethylcyanoacrylate (CA), “Super-Moment” adhesive and the other with delaminated or separate (clenched) layers. The initial ‘rod’ part of the waveguide provides optimal conditions for a soliton formation and ensures that it is really a soliton entering the layered part under study. Note that our previous experiments showed that the CA adhesive is close in elastic features to those of PMMA and PS (see Table 1 for elastic characteristics of both polymers and CA adhesive) and does not introduce any significant distortions in the strain soliton behaviour ([5]). Wave patterns inside the waveguide were recorded using the technique of classical ‘analogue’ holographic interferometry, providing observation of bulk density waves in an optically transparent waveguide via wave-induced local variations of the refractive index of the waveguide. The basic schematic of the experimental setup is shown in Fig. 2.

	Density	Young modulus	Poisson ratio	3 rd order elastic moduli (Murnaghan)			Nonlinearity coefficient	Sound velocity (rod)
	ρ g/cm ³	E GPa	ν	l GPa	m GPa	n GPa	β GPa	C_r m/s
PS	1.06	4.03	0.34	-18.9	-13.3	-10.0	-35.3	1870
PMMA	1.16	5.27	0.34	-10.9	-7.7	-1.4	-15.9	2080
CA	1.05	2.76						

Table 1. Elastic parameters of PS, PMMA and CA adhesive.

Figure 1. Schematic of the soliton generation arrangement

Figure 2. Basic schematic of the holographic setup.

2.2 Interferogram processing

The interferogram processing procedure includes measurements of fringe shifts with succeeding calculations of wave parameters: amplitude and length. Various defects in interference fringes, discontinuities in particular, complicate or even preclude automatic fringe tracking and interferogram processing by means of known algorithms. We have recently demonstrated ([10]) the possibility to process classical holographic interferograms in finite width fringes using algorithms developed for reconstruction of off-axis digital holograms (e.g. [11-13]) and specifically those sustainable to fringe discontinuities, e.g. [13].

The soliton parameters can be directly obtained from the fringe shifts on interferograms or from the reconstructed arrays of phase retardation values in the following way. In classical case the soliton amplitude can be calculated from the fringe shift by the formula:

$$A = \frac{\Delta K \lambda}{h(n_1 - 1)(1 - \nu)} \quad (1)$$

where ΔK is the fringe shift, λ is the recording laser wavelength (0,694 μm), n_1 is the refractive index of the material, h is the waveguide thickness along the recording laser beam (10 mm), ν is the Poisson ratio. Since $\Delta K = \varphi/2\pi$ (where φ is phase), for the phase retardation data we obtain:

$$A = \frac{\varphi\lambda}{2\pi h(n_1 - 1)(1 - \nu)} \quad (2)$$

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Soliton in the uniform bar

The typical interferogram of the formed bulk strain soliton in the uniform PMMA bar is shown in Figure 3. The soliton is a rather long-length symmetrical bell-shaped longitudinal wave, which is not followed by any tensile wave. As reported in [1] the soliton propagates in a uniform waveguide for a long distance showing very low decay.

Figure 3. Holographic interferogram of the formed strain soliton in the uniform PMMA bar. (Hereinafter waves move from left to right.)

3.2 Solitons in layered bars made of the same material

An adhesively bonded layered waveguide with delamination area(s) is a relatively complicated structure that provides different perturbations for an elastic wave propagating in it. First, elastic characteristics of an adhesive differ from those of the waveguide material, introducing a ‘longitudinal’ inhomogeneity along the entire path of the soliton. Then, an abrupt change of waveguide parameters, both geometrical (the separated layers instead of a single bonded waveguide) and elastic (absence of the adhesive layer) in the delamination area produces the step-like inhomogeneity in transverse direction. Note also that the number of bonded layers affects the soliton behavior as well due to the change of geometrical characteristics of a single layer. As a result of the aforementioned factors the parameters of the soliton propagating in such structures may vary (amplitude and width) and additional disturbances (complex wave patterns) may be generated. Some of these effects have been analyzed and reported recently (see [6,8]).

The summary of the soliton behaviour in the CA-bonded and delaminated layered bars is as follows. In the completely bonded bar the logarithmic decay rate of solitons is only slightly greater than that in the uniform bar made of the same material. The delamination leads to the distinctive increase of the soliton amplitude in the delaminated area, which depends on the number of layers. The thinner are the layers the higher is the soliton amplitude. While propagating along the waveguide with delamination the soliton decays, however its amplitude remains higher than that of a soliton in a uniform bar. The variations of the leading soliton amplitude in the delaminated bar is accompanied by the generation of additional disturbances, namely, soliton trains (see Fig. 4 depicting the soliton train in the delaminated area of the three-layered PMMA bar).

Figure 4. Holographic interferograms of the soliton train in the delaminated area of the 3-layered PMMA bar: lead soliton (a) and secondary soliton (b).

3.2 Solitons in layered bars made of different materials

The experiments were performed using two specimens in the form of two-layered waveguides with layers made of PMMA and PS. Layers of the first specimen were completely delaminated and clenched together. Layers in the second specimen were completely bonded by the CA adhesive. In both configurations the layered part of the waveguide was bonded to the initial part (PMMA rod) by the CA adhesive.

Figure 5. Holographic interferograms of the strain solitons in a bar with delaminated layers made of PS and PMMA at the distance 20-70 mm from the layered part input at the two time moments.

Figure 5 presents interferograms of wave patterns in the waveguide with delaminated layers at the same distance from the waveguide input (70-120 mm) but at two succeeding time moments. Obviously wave patterns in the layers differ quite noticeably, solitons in the materials propagate with different velocities, characteristic for each material. Their amplitudes are noticeably different. Moreover in the PMMA layer one can observe the formation of a soliton train, which is in complete correspondence with our previous experiments (see Fig. 4) and developed theory [8]. We can conclude that in this case the initial soliton enters two separate layers of PS and PMMA and then propagates through them independently. Due to the difference in velocities (1870 m/s in PS and 2080 m/s in PMMA) the soliton in the upper layer (PS) lags behind the soliton in the lower layer (PMMA). The soliton amplitude in the PS layer is much lower than that in the PMMA layer. This difference is due to two factors. First, at the transverse junction of the PMMA rod and PS layer a part of the soliton energy is reflected back owing to the difference in acoustic impedances of the materials. And second is a consequence of the difference in refractive indices of the materials (1.49 for PMMA and 1.59 for PS) resulting in a slightly different fringe shift for the same density variation (see eq. 1).

The wave patterns shown in Figure 6, where the PS and PMMA layers are bonded together with the CA adhesive, are quite different – a combined solitary wave is formed propagating in the layered structure with the joint velocity and exhibiting joint amplitude and shape. Note that the waveguide

area covered by the two interferograms in Fig. 6 comprises 100 mm which equals to three soliton widths and would be sufficient to detect soliton separation in the layers, if any.

Figure 6. Holographic interferograms of the strain soliton in the bar with bonded layers made of PS and PMMA at the distance 20-70 mm (a) and 70-120 mm (b) from the layered part input.

Figure 7 presents strain soliton in the two-layered CA-bonded bar made of PMMA and PMMA + fullerene black (1% wt) layers. The strain soliton has almost the same amplitude and shape as in the 2-layered PMMA bar. That proves the existence of strain solitons in this modified composite polymeric material. Note that in the layered structure made of PMMA and polyethylene (the material where strain solitons cannot exist) the soliton propagating in the PMMA layer vanishes completely at the distance of about 70 mm from the layered part input.

Figure 7. Holographic interferogram of the soliton in the bonded two-layered bar made of PMMA and PMMA + fullerene black at the distance 70-120 mm from the layered bar input.

4 CONCLUSIONS

Summarizing the results obtained we conclude:

In the bonded area of the layered waveguide with layers made of the same material the soliton parameter values are close to those in the uniform waveguide of the same geometry, with somewhat higher attenuation. When the soliton enters the delamination area, the increase of the leading soliton amplitude is observable, and the soliton train is generated. When propagating again into the bonded area the second soliton attenuates relatively fast, and the leading soliton also suffers attenuation, but its resulting amplitude remains higher than the amplitude of the soliton in completely bonded bar at the same distance.

In the bonded area of the layered waveguide with layers made of different materials (but both allowing soliton formation) the single generalized soliton is formed propagating in the layered structure as a unified entity. When entering the delamination area this combined soliton splits into independent ones propagating in each material with own speed. Soliton trains are generated as well.

This behaviour is also valid for combinations of (nano)composite materials and their base matrix materials. That is essential since a vast majority of nanocomposites is opaque and do not allow for translucent recording of wave patterns.

The observed phenomena may be applied for delamination detection in various layered construction elements.

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